

Review on Steel Fibers Reinforced Concrete

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Abstract— Concrete is one of the world's most widely used construction material. However, since the early 1800's, it has been known that concrete is weak in capable of tension. decrepit combined with brittle behavior result in sudden ductile failure without warning. This is obviously not desirable for any building product. Thus, concrete requires some form of tensile fortification to compensate its brittle behavior and improve its normal stress and tension capacity to be used in structural applications. Historically, steel has been used as the material of choice for capable of tension reinforcement in concrete. Fiber Reinforced solid (FRs) is defined as a composite material essentially consisting of conventional concrete or mortar reinforced by the random dispersal of short, discontinuous, and discrete fine fibers of specific geometry. further research and development on fiber reinforced solid (FRC) has been initiated. The present aspect of this research is that how we utilize fibers of steel in structural solid elements for enhancing the concrete's mechanical property. Also, the purpose of this research is to determine automatically properties of concrete and the comparison of these properties with containing and without containing fibers.

Keywords— VAWT, wind power generation, highway, wind utilization

I. INTRODUCTION

The study aims to provide insights into the performance and durability of this innovative construction material. As a student an introduction to the important properties of engineering materials with special reference to the concrete is very important the other properties such as strength, toughness, dimensional stability, durability. As a student an introduction to the important properties of engineering materials with special reference to the concrete is very important the other properties such as strength, toughness, dimensional stability, durability and other mechanical

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properties of concrete. This chapter describes importance of concrete its applications and examines the reason's that made concrete the most widely and accepted used structural material in the world today.

II. OBJECTIVES

Study the strength properties of concrete using steel fibers with variations and compare it with conventional concrete Insights into the performance and durability of SFRC through experimental investigation comprehensive evaluations of stress dimensional stability durability and mechanical properties of SFRC.

III. DIFFERENT TYPES OF FIBERS

Various types of steel are available for reinforcing concrete Including hooked, crimped and straight fibers types offers Unique benefits in terms of bonding with concrete matrix and improving compressive strength.

A. Applications of SFRCs

Nowadays, SFRC is employed at associate increasing rate in varied applications like the followings

- 1) Highway and air-field pavements
- 2) Hydraulic Structures
- 3) To control cracking due to plastic
- 4) To control cracking due to shrinkage
- 5) To increased durability

Table 1: Physical Properties of Steel Fiber

Sr. No.	Property	Values
1	Diameter	0.75 mm
2	Length of fiber	60 mm
3	Appearance	Bright in clean wire
4	Average aspect ratio	80
6	Deformation	Hooked at both ends
7	Tensile strength	1050 MPa

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

Milind V Mohd (2012) et al in this experimental investigation for M30 grade of solid to study the compressive strength and tensile strength of steel fibers reinforced concrete containing fibers varied by 0.25%, 0.5% 1% 1.5% and 2% by volume of cement cubes of size 150mmX150mmX150mm to check the compressive strength and beams of size 500mmX100mmX100mm for checking flexural strength were casted. All the specimens were cured for the period OF 3, 7 and 28 days before insufferable the result of fibers reinforced concrete 3 days, 7 days, and 28 days healing with varied percentage of fiber were studied and it has been found that there is significant strength development Development in steel fiber reinforced concrete. The maximum fiber content while studying the compressive strength of cube is found to be 10% and 0.75% for bend strength of the beam. Also, it has been distinguishing that with the increase in fiber content up to the maximum value increase the strength of concrete.

Vikrant Vairagade et al (2012) presented the applicability of previously published relation among compressive strength tensile strength bend strength of normal concrete to steel fibers reinforced concrete was evaluated and mechanical properties of steel reinforced concrete were analyzed in this investigation study cement sand coarse aggregate water and steel fibers were used for compressive strength test both cube specimens of dimensions 150mm × 150mm × 150mm and circular specimen of length 200mm and diameter 100mm were cast for M20 grade filled with 0% and 0.5% fibers after 24 hours the specimens were to curing tank wherein they were allowed cure for 7 days and 28 days. Finally, consequence of condense strength for M20 grade of concrete on cube and cylinder specimens with 0% and 0.5% steel fibers for for cast ratio 50 and 53.85 is it observed that for addition of 0.5% fibers shows slightly more compressive strength than normal concrete

Prof. Ram Meghe et al (2014) presented the experimental study of the steel fibers reinforced self-compacting concrete by addition of different content of steel fibers the result showed that the split tensile strength found to be increased with the addition of steel fibers and the optimum fiber content for increasing the split tensile strength was found to be 1.75% it was been observed that the steel fibers are used in the concrete to give the maximum strength as compared to other fibers such as glass fibers polypropylene fibers. The compressive strength and the flexural strength observed to be increased as the percentage of steel fibers are increased in the steel fibers reinforced concrete.

Elson John et al (2014) in this study it was observed that the physical properties of the concrete after adding the different volume fractions of fibers are used in the concrete. In the mix design is carried out as per 10262:2009 the proportioning is carried out to achieve strength at specified age, workability of fresh and durability requirements. The materials selected for this experimental study includes normal

B. Types of Materials

1. Cement
2. Sand
3. Aggregate
4. Fibers

Test on Materials Finess test on cement Soundness test on Aggregate
Test on Fresh Concrete

C. Slump cone test

Test on Hardness concrete Compressive strength Test
Compressive strength of concrete is the Strength of solidity solid measured by the compression test. The constriction strength of solid is a compute of the concrete's capability to resist loads which tend to compress it. It is computed by crushing cubical concrete specimens in compression testing machine.

D. Experimental Investigation of the Project

We study the about mechanical properties of steel fibers and we study about grade of concrete and we will test raw Material and we conduct to tests on fresh concrete and after that we will test on hardens of concrete.

natural coarse aggregate, manufactured sand as fine aggregate, cement, Superplasticizer both end hooked steel fibers and portable drinking water.

REFERENCES

- [1] 1p . Kumar Mehta and Paulo J M Monterio Concrete microstructure, properties, and materials, Tata McGraw-Hill Third edition pg.501
- [2] ACI Committee 544.1R, (1996) Fiber reinforced concrete, American concrete institute, Michigan, USA
- [3] ACI Committee 544 "Guide for Specifying, Mixing, Placing, and Finishing Steel.
- [4] Barros JAO, FigueirasJA (1992), Flexural Behavior of SFRC, testing and Modeling,a. Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering, Vol 11, No.4.
- [5] Shah Surendra and Rangan (1994), Effect of Fiber addition on concrete strength,
- [6] Gopalaratnam, V. S. et al. (1991). Fracture toughness of fiber reinforced concrete. IACI Material Journal, 88(4) 339-353
- [7] Ali R. Khaloo and Majida Shari Flexural behavior of small steel fiber
- [8] Rossi P, Acker P, Malier Y. (1987) Effect of steel fibers at two different stages, The Material and the Structures, Vol.20, pp.34-39.
- [9] L. G. Sorelli, A. Meda, and G. A. Plizzari (2005), Bending and Uniaxial Tensile Tests on Concrete Reinforced with Hybrid Steel Fibers, Journ Material in Civil Experimental Research and Numerical Simulation, Journal of Structural Engineering..